

FUNKSIYALARNI LAGRANJ INTERPOLYATSION FORMULASI YORDAMIDA APPROKSIMATSIYALASH MASALASINI DASTURLASH HAQIDA

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ABSTRACT

Tajribadan ma'lumki, funksiyalarni Lagranj interpolatsion formulasi yordamida approksimatsiyalash bo'yicha mavzusini o'zlashtirishda talabalar ancha qiyinchiliklarga duch keladilar. Ushbu maqolada dastlab asosiy tushunchalarni keltirib, masala tanlab, uni Lagranj interpolatsion formulasi yordamida yechib, unga tuzilgan dastur kodini keltiramiz va natijalarni solishtiramiz.

f(x) funksiya [a, b] oraliqda aniqlangan bo'lsin, ushbu oraliqda f(x) va phi(x) funksiyalarning yaqinligi ta'minlangan bo'lsin. Berilgan kesmada

a <= x0 < x1 < x2 < ... < xn <= b

shart bo'yicha nuqtalar to'plami, ya'ni tugunlarni tanlab olamiz. Bunda tugunlarning

soni F(x)=phi(x, C_bar)=c1phi1(x)+c2phi2(x)+...+cnphin(x)=sum_k=1^n ck*phi_k(x) tenglikdagi C_bar parametrlar soniga teng. Bu tugunlarda f(x) funksiyaning qiymatlari ma'lum, ya'ni yi=f(x_i), i=0, n.

Interpolyatsiya masalasi F(x)=phi(x, C_bar)=c1phi1(x)+c2phi2(x)+...+cnphin(x)=sum_k=1^n ck*phi_k(x) ga mos ko'phadlarni tanlashga olib kelinadi:

P(x) = c_0*x^n + c_1*x^{n-1} + ... + c_{n-1}*x + c_n = sum_k=0^n c_k*x^{n-k}

Bunda c_k koeffitsiyentlar haqiqiy sonlardan iborat bo'lib, quyidagi qoida asosida topiladi:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n c_k x_i^{n-k} = f(x_i) = y_i, \quad i = \overline{0, n}.$$

Ma'lumki, bunday ko'phadga interpolyatsion ko'phad deyiladi.

$$\sum_{k=0}^n c_k x_i^{n-k} = f(x_i) = y_i, \quad i = \overline{0, n}. \quad \text{shart} \quad \text{qo'llanadigan}$$

$$P(x) = c_0 x^n + c_1 x^{n-1} + \dots + c_{n-1} x + c_n = \sum_{k=0}^n c_k x^{n-k}, \quad \text{amaliyotga global interpolyatsiya deyiladi.}$$

Agar $P(x) = c_0 x^n + c_1 x^{n-1} + \dots + c_{n-1} x + c_n = \sum_{k=0}^n c_k x^{n-k}$ ko'phad $f(x)$ funksiyaning aniqlanish sohasi bo'lgan $[a, b]$ kesmaning faqat alohida qismlari uchun, ya'ni $m < n$ bo'lgan m ta interpolyatsion tugun uchun qurilsa, u holda interpolyatsiyani lokal interpolyatsiya deyiladi.

Lagranj interpolatsiya formulasi, berilgan n ta nuqta orasidagi funksiyaning approksimatsiyasini topish uchun ishlatiladi. Bu formulaning asosiy ideyasi, berilgan n ta nuqta orasidagi funksiyaning bir nechta polinomlarga bo'linishi va har bir polinomni o'zining x qiymatida hisoblashdir. Lagranj interpolatsiyasi formulasi quyidagicha ifodalash mumkin:

Umumiy ko'rinishdagi interpolyatsiyada interpolyatsion ko'phad x_T ning aniqlanish

$$P(x) = c_0 x^n + c_1 x^{n-1} + \dots + c_{n-1} x + c_n = \sum_{k=0}^n c_k x^{n-k},$$

sohasida barcha intervallar uchun

$$\varphi(x) = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + \dots + a_n x^n.$$

ko'rinishda izlanadi, ya'ni $[x_0, x_n]$ uchun:

$$a_i \text{ koeffitsiyentlarni aniqlash uchun } \sum_{k=0}^n c_k x_i^{n-k} = f(x_i) = y_i, \quad i = \overline{0, n}. \quad \text{tenglamalar}$$

sistemi tuziladi:

$$\begin{cases} a_0 + a_1 x_0 + \dots + a_n x_0^n = y_0; \\ a_0 + a_1 x_1 + \dots + a_n x_1^n = y_1; \\ \dots \\ a_0 + a_1 x_n + \dots + a_n x_n^n = y_n. \end{cases}$$

Ma'lumki, agar $i \neq j$ lar uchun $x_i \neq x_j$ shart o'rinli bo'lsa, tenglamalar sistemasi yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi. Keltirilgan tenglamalar sistemasini yechish uchun chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini yechish usullaridan foydalansa ham bo'ladi. Tenglamalar sistemasini to'g'ridan to'g'ri yechib, $F(x)$ funksiyani $\varphi(x) = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + \dots + a_n x^n$ ko'rinishida olish ham mumkin, bunda bir nechta hisoblashlar bitta jadval bo'yicha bajariladi.

$y = f(x_T)$ ni bir martalik hisoblash uchun \vec{a} vektor parametrlarini topish shart bo'lmagan boshqa algoritmlar mavjud. Interpolyatsion ko'phadlar esa $\{x_i, y_i\}, i = \overline{0, n}$ jadval qiymatlari orqali yoziladi. Bular Lagranj va Nyuton interpolyatsion ko'phadlaridir.

Quyidagi misolni Lagranj interpolatsion formulasi yordamida yechamiz: Jadval bilan berilgan $y=f(x)$ funksiya qiymatini $x = 2.5$ bo'lgan hol uchun hisoblaymiz:

i	0	1	2	3	4
x_i	1	2	3	4	5
y_i	2	4	1	7	3

$$L_n(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n y_j \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n \frac{x - x_i}{x_j - x_i}$$

Masalani quyidagicha yechamiz: yozib olamiz:

ga asosan ishchi formulani

$$L(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n y_i \prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i}}^n \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j}$$

Bizning holda $n = 4$ gacha, shu sababli:

$$\begin{aligned} L(x) &= \sum_{i=0}^4 y_i \prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i}}^4 \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} = \\ &= y_0 \frac{(x - x_1)(x - x_2)(x - x_3)(x - x_4)}{(x_0 - x_1)(x_0 - x_2)(x_0 - x_3)(x_0 - x_4)} + y_1 \frac{(x - x_0)(x - x_2)(x - x_3)(x - x_4)}{(x_1 - x_0)(x_1 - x_2)(x_1 - x_3)(x_1 - x_4)} + \\ &+ y_2 \frac{(x - x_1)(x - x_0)(x - x_3)(x - x_4)}{(x_2 - x_0)(x_2 - x_1)(x_2 - x_3)(x_2 - x_4)} + y_3 \frac{(x - x_0)(x - x_1)(x - x_2)(x - x_4)}{(x_3 - x_0)(x_3 - x_1)(x_3 - x_2)(x_3 - x_4)} + y_4 \frac{(x - x_0)(x - x_1)(x - x_2)(x - x_3)}{(x_4 - x_0)(x_4 - x_1)(x_4 - x_2)(x_4 - x_3)} = \end{aligned}$$

Berilgan jadval asosida, xususan, $n=1$ va $x_T = 2.5$ bo'lgan hol uchun Lagranj ko'phadini tuzamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} L(x) &= \sum_{i=0}^1 y_i \prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i}}^1 \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} = y_0 \frac{x - x_1}{x_0 - x_1} + y_1 \frac{(x - x_0)}{(x_1 - x_0)} = \\ &= 2 * \frac{x - 2}{1 - 2} + 4 * \frac{(x - 1)}{(2 - 1)} = 6x - 8; \end{aligned}$$

Bu esa chiziqli interpolatsion formula bilan ustma-ust tushadi. Berilgan jadval asosida $n=2$ va $x_T = 2.5$ bo'lgan hol uchun Lagranj ko'phadini tuzamiz:

$$y \approx L(x) = \sum_{i=0}^2 y_i \prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i}}^2 \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j};$$

Qaralayotgan $[x_1, x_4]$ intervalda

$$\begin{aligned} x_0 &= 2; & x_1 &= 3; & x_2 &= 4; & x_3 &= 5; \\ y_0 &= 4; & y_1 &= 1; & y_2 &= 7; & y_3 &= 3; \end{aligned}$$

qiymatlarni olamiz. U holda 2-tartibli Lagranj interpolatsion ko'phadi hosil bo'ladi:

$$\begin{aligned} y \approx L(x) &= 4 \cdot \frac{(x - 3)(x - 4)(x - 5)}{(2 - 3)(2 - 4)(2 - 5)} + 1 \cdot \frac{(x - 1)(x - 5)(x - 2)}{(3 - 2)(3 - 4)(3 - 5)} + 7 \cdot \frac{(x - 2)(x - 3)(x - 5)}{(4 - 2)(4 - 3)(4 - 5)} + \\ &+ 3 \cdot \frac{(x - 2)(x - 4)(x - 3)}{(5 - 2)(5 - 3)(5 - 4)} = 0.278x^3 - 10.1x^2 - 49.39x - 63.2 \end{aligned}$$

$$x = 2.5 \text{ bo'lganda } y \approx L(x) = 1.47656$$

Shunday qilib, Lagranj interpolatsiyasi formulasi yordamida funksiyaning approksimatsiyasini topish uchun, biz berilgan n ta nuqta orasidagi funksiya qiymatlaridan foydalanib, Lagranj polinomlarini hisoblaymiz va ularni funksiya qiymatlariga ko'paytirib, yig'indisini hisoblaymiz. Shu yig'indidan hosil bo'lgan qiymat esa approksimatsiya qilingan nuqtaga mos keladi.

Funksiyani Lagranj interpolatsion formulasi yordamida tuzilgan dasturni keltiramiz:

//Yoqubov Shehroz C++ da Lagranj interpolatsion formulasi dasturi

```
#include <iostream>
```

```
#include <vector>
```

```
#include <cmath>
```

```
using namespace std;
```

```
double lagrange_interpolation(vector<double> x, vector<double> y, double xi) {
```

```
    double yi = 0;
```

```
    int n = x.size();
```

```
    for (int i = 0; i < n; i++) {
```

```
        double term = y[i];
```

```
        for (int j = 0; j < n; j++) {
```

```
            if (i != j) {
```

```
                term *= (xi - x[j]) / (x[i] - x[j]);
```

```
            }
```

```
        }
```

```
        yi += term;
```

```
    }
```

```
    return yi;
```

```
}
```

```
int main() {
```

```
    vector<double> x = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5};
```

```
    vector<double> y = {2, 4, 1, 7, 3};
```

```
    double xi = 2.5;
```

```
    double yi = lagrange_interpolation(x, y, xi);
```

```
    cout << "f(" << xi << ") = " << yi << endl;
```

```
    return 0;
```

```
}
```

Dastur natijasi quyudagicha boladi.


```
3 #include <vector>
4 #include <cmath>
5 using namespace std;
6
7 double lagrange_interpolation(vector<double> x, vector<double> y, double xi) {
8     double yi = 0;
9     int n = x.size();
10
11     for (int i = 0; i < n; i++) {
12         double term = y[i];
13
14         for (int j = 0; j < n; j++) {
15             if (i != j) {
16                 term *= (xi - x[j]) / (x[i] - x[j]);
17             }
18         }
19
20         yi += term;
21     }
22
23     return yi;
24 }
25
26 int main() {
27     vector<double> x = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5};
28     vector<double> y = {2, 4, 1, 7, 3};
29
30     double xi = 2.5;
31     double yi = lagrange_interpolation(x, y, xi);
32
33     cout << "f(" << xi << ") = " << yi << endl;
34
35     return 0;
36 }
37
```

f(2.5) = 1.47656

$f(x)$ ushbu kod biz taxmin qilmoqchi bo'lgan funksiyani belgilaydi. Bu kod, Lagranj interpolatsiya formulasini va test ma'lumotlarini (x va y) o'z ichiga olgan C++ dasturidir. Test ma'lumotlari orqali $f(2.5)$ qiymatini hisoblaydi.

Dastur Lagranj interpolatsiya formulasini, x va y koordinatalarining ro'yxatlarini olib, berilgan x_i nuqtasidagi qiymatni hisoblayadi. Bu usul bir nechta nuqtalardan o'tkazilgan grafiklarni interpolatsiyalash uchun qo'llaniladi.

" x " " xs " " i " " $interpolate(x, xs, ys)$ " " $f(x)$ " " x " " xs " " ys " " $[a, b]$ " " h " " h_interp " " $f(x)$ ".

Dastur natijasi taxminan = 1.4765 ga teng, ya'ni hisoblangan natija bilan deyarli bir xil $y \approx L(x) = 1.47656$.

Ushbu maqolada keltirilgan Lagranj interpolatsion formulasi yordamida yechilib, dasturi tuzilgan masaladan talabalar mavzuni o'zlashtirishda foydalanishlari mumkin, shuningdek, undan foydalanib mavzuga doir berilgan topshiriqlarni bajarishlari mumkin. O'ylaymizki, talabalar keltirilgan natijalardan foydalanib, oliy matematika fani masalalarini dasturlash bilan bog'lab o'rganadilar.

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